

Analysis of “Waka” by Michiko Toyama: Cultural Influence on the Creation of the First Electroacoustic Music by a Japanese Woman

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Abstract

Michiko Toyama (1913-2006) was the first Japanese woman composer of electroacoustic music. Yet she has long been unrecognized and sometimes even ignored in the history of music in Japan and the world. Toyama led an unusual life. She was born in Osaka and began her formal piano performance studies in early age. In the 1930s, she went to Paris to study piano with Henri Gil-Marchex. In 1936 and thereafter, she studied composition with Nadia Boulanger at École Normale de Musique de Paris. As a result, her ensemble piece "Yamato No Koe (The Voice of Yamato)" was selected for the Fifteenth ISCM World Music Days in Paris in 1937. Toyama became the first Japanese composer to be chosen for this prestigious festival of contemporary music. After World War II, she studied composition with Darius Milhaud and Olivier Messiaen at the Paris Conservatory, where she met Pierre Schaeffer and learned about the creation of musique concrète. Later, she moved to New York in 1956 as a visiting composer at Columbia University. She studied with Vladimir Ussachevsky and Otto Luening, who had been creating electronic music since around 1951, long before the Columbia-Princeton Electronic Music Center was formally established in 1958. At the CPEMC, Toyama composed two electroacoustic tape pieces, "Waka" and "Aoi No Ue," in 1958 and 1959, respectively. "Waka" may be regarded as one of the earliest electroacoustic fixed music compositions by women. But "Waka" was initially planned to be a piece for a narrator on stage, accompanied by electroacoustic music. The score was written in standard music notation for flute, cello, and a narrative component. Her music shows sensitivity in the transformation between timbres and intonation in the phrases. This research focuses on how the score, representing what Toyama imagined, was realized in the 1960 recording for Smithsonian Folkways Records. The piece's cultural influence will also be closely examined.

1. Introduction

Michiko Toyama (1913–2006) was the first Japanese composer selected for the ISCM International Society for Contemporary Music's "World Music Days" with an award, and the first Japanese woman to compose electroacoustic music. Despite this, she has long been forgotten in the annals of global music history. Gender and political issues seem to have a major influence. As this topic diverges from music, it will be left to scholars with specialized

knowledge. This study highlights the relationship between Toyama's unusual life and work, examining her exceptional musicality influenced by Japanese culture.

The subject of this study, "Waka" is a work for narration and electroacoustic music. While alternate scores for this work remain, this study focuses on the version created for flute, cello, and electroacoustic parts, dated 1958. The handwritten score was acquired by Columbia University's Music Library (now the Gabe M. Wiener Music & Arts Library) in 1958, shortly after its composition. The narration section features twelve waka poems, a form of classical Japanese literature. The arrangement of these pieces creates a compelling narrative, highlighting the delicate transitions in the timbre and intonation of the phrases.

Works like this, in which the electroacoustic part is written first as an instrumental piece, can also be found in early pieces, such as Milton Babbitt's "Phonemena." Historically, as the shift from twelve-tone technique to total serialism saw contemporary composers see a future in electroacoustic music as a way to recreate music so complex that it was almost impossible for performers to play. Considering this, the process of writing the score first and then realizing it electronically in "Waka" seems reasonable. Interestingly, while Babbitt's work faithfully reproduces pitches, Waka's realization reflects a slightly different composer's perspective. This reveals the perspective of a composer who created a piece that reflects the traditions of Japanese music, which distinguishes it from the history of Western music, which focuses primarily on pitch sharpening. This research compares what can be read from handwritten scores with what can be heard from recordings included in Toyama's first and last music album, "WAKA and Other Compositions," published in 1960 by Smithsonian Folkways Records in the United States, to consider how the composer transformed sketches, or the sounds in her head, into electroacoustic music, and whether cultural background influenced this.

2. Brief Biography & Toyama's Path to the New Medium

Toyama lived an unusual life that deviated greatly from the lifestyle of the average woman in Japan at the time. What is most noteworthy is that she studied abroad in Paris twice, in the 1930s and 1950s, and then in New York in the late 1950s. This chapter will briefly trace her life from her time in Paris to her time in New York.

2.1. Two Studies in Paris and His Encounter with Electroacoustic Music

Born in 1913 to a wealthy family in Osaka, Toyama began formal piano studies at an early age and, around 1930, when she was 17, went to Paris to study. During her first visit to Paris, she did not attend music school but instead took private lessons from Henri Gil-Marchex, honing her skills as a pianist. It was during this time that she had a fateful encounter with Nadia Boulanger, a professor at the École Normale de Musique and a renowned teacher who had nurtured numerous outstanding composers at the Fontainebleau American Conservatory from 1921 onward. After studying under Boulanger for just a year from 1936, Toyama became the first Japanese, and indeed an Asian, composer to win a prestigious award at the 15th ICMA World Music Days Festival in Paris the following year, with her chamber work "Yamato No Koe" (Ancient Voices). However, fate did not favor her. In 1939, just as she was expanding her activities as a composer based in Paris, World War II broke out in Europe. Forced to return to Japan, she married in 1941 and had two children. She lost her husband in the war in 1945, the year the war ended, and was widowed at the age of 32. From 1948 to 1951, she taught at Osaka

College of Music, but returned to Paris in 1952. During her second stay in Paris, she studied composition with Darius Milhaud and Olivier Messiaen and counterpoint with Noel Gallon at the Conservatoire National Supérieur de Musique de Paris. It was there, through Pierre Schaeffer, who was a special lecturer in Messiaen's class, that she discovered "Musique Concrète." The commentary for the album "WAKA and Other Compositions," published in 1960 by Smithsonian Folkways Records, includes the following facts in Toyama's own words:

During my second visit to France, when I was studying composition at the Paris Conservatoire, one afternoon in 1952, Pierre Schaeffer was invited as a guest to our composition class to demonstrate "Musique Concrète." Hearing a sound composed of sounds that sounded more like noise than music, there was a general air of disappointment among the students in the class, but I was one of the few students who was moved.¹

At age 24, Toyama was selected for the ISCM-WMD and, upon returning to Japan, secured a position as an associate professor at Osaka College of Music. But what were Toyama's thoughts and circumstances that led her to leave her two children in the care of her parents and head to Paris for a second time, just before turning 40? While already well-versed in the compositional techniques of a contemporary composer, she must have been searching for a new perspective on musical creation. Her encounter with electroacoustic music, introduced to her by Schaeffer, left her deeply moved, yet she never set foot in Schaeffer's Radio France studio, nor did she have the opportunity to create electroacoustic works during her time in Paris. However, there's no doubt that the possibilities of musical creation through electroacoustic music at least opened new eyes to her.

2.2. Creating Electroacoustic Music in America

Around the time Toyama returned to Paris and met Schaeffer, tape recorders were introduced at Columbia University's School of Music around 1951. Vladimir Ussachevsky and Otto Luening were creating their early works as they moved from one location to another. They held America's first public electronic music concert at the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) on October 28, 1952. Luciano Berio, inspired by this performance, founded Studio di Fonologia Musicale di Radio Milano at the Italian Broadcasting Corporation RAI in Milan in 1955 with Bruno Maderna.

When Toyama moved to New York in 1956, the studio was in the Pre-Columbia-Princeton Electronic Music Center (1951-57) period, known as the Columbia Tape Music Center, the first electronic music studio in America, on the Columbia University campus in Manhattan. With support from the Rockefeller Foundation, preparations were underway for the official founding of the CPEMC. The electronic music studio, now renamed the Computer Music Center, located on 125th Street in Manhattan, was planned and run by two Columbia University professors, Ussachevsky and Luening, and two Princeton University professors, Roger Sessions and Milton Babbitt, from the pre-CPEMC era.

¹ Liner notes: TOYAMA, Michiko. "Waka and Other Compositions: Contemporary Music of Japan. Based on Traditional Japanese Themes and Poetry Composed by Michiko Toyama". Washington DC, Smithsonian Folkways Recordings (FW8881), 2007.

Toyama, who had studied in Paris twice, has often been asked why she moved to New York rather than return to Paris. First, from 1921 to 1979, Nadia Boulanger taught at the American Conservatory's composition department, which has been regarded as the world's oldest music festival, held at the Château de Fontainebleau. Boulanger's former students included renowned American composers such as Aaron Copland, Elliott Carter, and Leonard Bernstein. Boulanger's deep involvement in the festival, which strengthened ties between the French and American music communities, may have helped connect young composers from both countries. Perhaps this was part of the story, as Toyama attended the Tanglewood Music Festival in the United States in 1955 and studied with Roger Sessions. While it remains unclear whether Boulanger actually had a close connection with Sessions, it's interesting to note that Copland served as director of the Tanglewood Music Center since its foundation in 1940, suggesting a connection from Boulanger to Copland to Sessions. Through Sessions, it's likely that she learned about the CPEMC, which was then in the final stages of preparation for its official launch, and decided to move to New York in 1956 in search of the possibility of actually creating electroacoustic music.

By this time, Toyama, already an experienced composer and educator, had been accepted as a visiting composer at Columbia University's Department of Music, and she studied the history of electronic music with Otto Luening and the production techniques of electroacoustic music with Vladimir Ussachevsky. Toyama also developed a close friendship with Edgard Varèse, who was working on the historic work "Poème Electronique" at the CPEMC during the same period. Varèse was not a faculty member in the music department but also a visiting composer. Considering the circumstances, it's unlikely that he had the influence to bring Toyama to New York.

In any case, in the new academic environment in the United States, where she gained free access to newly established studios, Toyama devoted herself to creating electroacoustic music. Her first work, "Waka," was completed in the summer of 1958. It was not incidental music but a concert piece of artistic electroacoustic music, the first of its kind to be composed by a woman at the CPEMC. Thus, Toyama became one of the first female composers to work in the field of electroacoustic music.

3. The Creation of "Waka" and the Technical Environment of CPEMC

1956, when Toyama moved to New York and enrolled at Columbia University, was still in the pre-CPEMC era, and 1958, when "Waka" was completed, was shortly after the CPEMC was officially founded. The main electroacoustic equipment used at the CPEMC at the time was a massive RCA Mark II Synthesizer,² which had just been installed in the studio, and it is not easy for composers with no engineering background and no experience with modular synthesizers to operate the Mark II by themselves, record, and complete tape works in such a short amount of time.

As Toyama herself writes in the commentary for Smithsonian Folkways Records, "Dr. Ussachevsky guided me to experiment at the laboratory," she may have received assistance from Ussachevsky in producing this piece. However, it typically takes several months to produce a six-and-a-half-minute-long analog tape piece, and it is unlikely that Ussachevsky, a

² <https://exhibitions.library.columbia.edu/exhibits/show/music-centennial/electronic-and-computer-music/electronic-music-center>

professor at Columbia University, would have been in the studio supervising Toyama throughout her production. As one reads further into the record's commentary, another person involved in the creation of "Waka" becomes apparent: Nobuo Yoneda (1930-1996), who graduated from the Faculty of Science at the University of Tokyo in 1952 and was studying at the Department of Mathematics at Columbia University on a Fulbright scholarship. Yoneda left behind a superb flute performance on this piece, and his participation as both a technical assistant and a flutist helped shape it during production.³

4. Literary and Musical Contents

In analyzing this work, it was first necessary to compare the sound with the score to assess how faithfully it was reproduced and, if there were any differences, how they were changed. Here, the analysis will proceed by comparing the narrative content with the musical content discernible from the recording.

4.1. Literary Characteristics and Structure

As the title suggests, "Waka" refers to waka poems, a form of classical Japanese literature. The track title of a 1960 recording reads "WAKA: Music for tape and narration read by Beate Gordon," suggesting that the piece was originally planned as a piece featuring an onstage narrator reciting English translations of waka poetry accompanied by and mixed with electroacoustic music from the speakers. This suggests the piece incorporates early live electronic elements. However, no documentation of the live performance has been found, and the album features the piece as a fixed-media, incorporating recorded narration.

The piece is divided into two movements, featuring five waka poems from the *Hyakunin Isshu* (One Hundred Poets, One Hundred Poets) translated into English by Kenneth Rexroth in the first movement and six in the second. *Hyakunin Isshu* generally refers to the *Ogura Hyakunin Isshu*, a collection of waka poems compiled by Fujiwara no Teika (1162-1241) during the Kamakura period. It is a particularly well-known form of classical literature, as those educated in Japan are likely exposed to it from an early age.

In fact, the third waka poem is not listed in the commentary. Its English inscription reads, "At last the dawn comes, through the cracks of the shutters, Heartless as night!" It is a poem lamenting the fact that dawn broke before the lover, whom the poet had waited all night for, appeared. The absence of any accompanying Japanese source material makes this poem a mystery, making it difficult to identify its original. The author's research has revealed that it does not appear to be included in the *Ogura Hyakunin Isshu*, and it may have been excerpted from another collection of waka poems. However, since any Japanese person with a knowledge of classical literature can compose a waka, it is not inconceivable that this mysterious poem was written by Toyama herself. If so, it could also be interpreted as a genuine expression of Toyama's feelings at the time.

Waka poems are limited to five lines, each consisting of 31 characters (5+7+5+7+7). They are like a microcosm of classical literature, capturing various human emotions and the vicissitudes

³ Liner notes: TOYAMA, Michiko. "Waka and Other Compositions: Contemporary Music of Japan. Based on Traditional Japanese Themes and Poetry Composed by Michiko Toyama". Washington DC, Smithsonian Folkways Recordings (FW8881), 2007.

of nature in a minimal number of words, using the unique layering of meanings and the ambiguity of the Japanese language. This makes them extremely difficult to translate, sometimes resulting in overly paraphrased or insufficient translations. Regardless of how they're translated, each word in the 31 characters is self-contained, preventing free rearrangement. Curiously, while working in New York, Toyama created this piece by reading aloud English translations of waka poems rather than in Japanese. The poems are narrated over electronic music, creating a different experience from reading them in Japanese.

The structure of this work is built around the unity of the words. Analyzing this work with this in mind, we can see the divisions between the five loosely spaced waka poems, as well as the existence of sections representing a higher level of unity. And what is surprising is that, although the poems are composed of different poems written by different people, when read as a whole, a story emerges as if it were a single literary work. This will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 8.

4.2. Japanese Rhythm

The opening score does not indicate a tempo or time signature, but it is written as eighth notes = 110 bpm. The first measure is written in $3/8$, and measures 2 through 10 are written as if they were $6/8$, with eighth notes added. However, the notation in measure 11 reveals that the actual time signature is $3/4$. In other words, what appears to be $3/8$ at the beginning is likely an upbeat beginning on the offbeat of the second beat of the $3/4$. In fact, the first note begins without a clear count, and the end of the section is unclear. While the notation suggests $6/8$ in the $3/4$ time signature, musically, the $9/8$ rhythmic units are repeated, making it extremely difficult to grasp the basic rhythm at the beginning of this piece without looking at the score. In measure 11, the final measure of this section, while the instrumental sounds are almost forced to stop moving, the fermata actually stops the beat, creating a sound that seems to stop time.

[Beginning 2 pages of Part 1]

Waka - 1st part

OCT 13 1958

for AKA Michiko Toyama

1 The wind rustles the bamboo by my window in the dusk

Taiko-like percussive sound (San No, Ko and Taiko? from Gagaku) begins the piece for 5 measures before narration enters

flute

From here another taiko-like sound in high register kakko(?) enters playing approximate pitches [F-C-B] respectively

cello

2 Not floats on the spring meadow My heart is lovely

Flute sounds like ryuteki from Gagaku

3 Nightingale sings in the dusk Yes, I am in love

4 F#E#-C-B 3/4 meter

5 They were talking about me before day light. Although

6 Sho-like sound enters in chords (without fingering)

7 I began to love without knowing it. Although I hide it, love shows in my face so plain - ly

8 Percussive sound

9 That he are you thinking of some thing?

10 Flute

11 Biwa-like sound

12 Biwa-like sound

13 Flute

14 Flute

15 Flute

16 Flute

17 Flute

18 Flute

19 Flute

20 Flute

21 Flute

22 Flute

23 Flute

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[Beginning 2 pages of part 2]

Waka - 2nd part

OCT 13 1958

for AKA Michiko Toyama

1 This morning... Sweet not comb my hair

Electronic music approach with Cello sounds (musique concrète-based technique)

2 It has lain pillow on the head of my love will he always love me?

3 I can not read his heart! This morning.

4 My thoughts are desorbed us my black hair

5 Unknown author's poem

6 It last the dawn

7 comes through the cracks of the shutters.

8 Heart has as night

9 Speed up

10 You do not come, and I wait on Matsuo beach in the

11 Electronic sound and point

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The piece begins with a slow, taiko-like sound that occasionally suggests a tempo but makes

the beat difficult to discern. The phrases then gradually become more detailed, eventually coalescing into a single section. This musical style is repeated throughout Part 1 and Part 2. It's clear that this music was created with jo-ha-kyu in mind. "Jo-ha-kyu" is a term related to the performance technique of gagaku. Originally, it referred to the three sections that make up a piece in gagaku's Tang music and other forms, equivalent to movements in Western music.

TOYAMA, Michiko. "Waka". Photocopy of manuscript, the Gabe M. Wiener Music & Arts Library. (Not published. Usage permitted by the family of the composer.)

As the concept of jo-ha-kyu spread and became established in traditional music other than gagaku, it was applied in a variety of ways, and the jo-ha-kyu technique began to be used not only in large structural units such as movements but also in phrases. The "jo" section is played freely, with no fixed beat set at a slow speed, and only the number of drum beats is determined. The beat is added in the "ha" section, and the piece accelerates in the "kyu" section, completing a three-part structure. However, not all of the "jo-ha-kyu" elements are present; many pieces have lost parts, or none existed in the first place.

The score is written so that the narration begins almost simultaneously with the percussion sounds at the beginning, but the actual sound is percussion sounds only for five bars, with the narration coming in at the sixth bar. As such, there are occasional parts that are not faithful to the score, which may suggest that this score is more of a sketch than the final version.

In the second part of the piece, the score is more complex and looks more like an instrumental piece. This can be seen as a combination of musique concrète in the electronic music gesture. During the same period of the 1950s and 1960s, many composers either used real sounds to be recognized or pure electronic, machine-made, pitch-oriented sounds as a better substitute for total serialism. But Toyama combines both in depth. She sometimes uses pure electronic sounds, but they don't become the main feature. For her, sonic gesture must have been the most important element in creating electroacoustic music. Especially in the second part, we can see her progress in creating the electroacoustic part. Since she was already an established composer by the time she went to the CPMEC, she could beautifully depict the scenes in the poems by the manipulation of electronic sounds.

4.3. Japanese Tone and Cultural Background

The percussion sounds used in this piece clearly resemble those of the traditional Japanese gagaku percussion instruments: the taiko drum, the sanno-tsuzumi drum, and the kakko drum. A flute melody emerges, featuring a distinctly high note. Listening to the flute's high notes amid this quiet introduction of percussion sounds certainly sounds like gagaku. Furthermore, since the only sounds in this piece, apart from the narration, are percussion and the flute, those familiar with traditional Japanese music may sense a "Japanese" quality just from listening to this opening section.

Incorporating elements of traditional Japanese music into electroacoustic music, which was cutting-edge in 1958, was a highly innovative endeavor. However, integrating traditional music, with its completely different approach to pitch and rhythm, into the idiom of electroacoustic music, which was based on Western music, must have presented significant challenges.

Listening to this piece after identifying the similarities and differences with gagaku, one notices that the flute sounds different. The flute's tone is very similar to that of the Ryuteki transverse flute used in gagaku music. When I first listened to the piece, before I found the sheet music, I struggled to realize that it also featured a cello in addition to a flute. But then, as a Japanese person, I began to understand why it had a certain nostalgic quality.

Here, it's important to remember that, as the title suggests, this piece is based on "Waka" (traditional Japanese poetry). The narration for the piece is made up of poems selected from the Hyakunin Isshu collection, many of which were written during the Heian period (8th to 12th centuries), the same period when gagaku music took on its current form. When considering sonic ideas based on waka, poetry recited in ancient vernacular, it's hard not to stray too far from that period, given that waka was the pastime of noble and intellectual people of ancient times.

5. Pitch-Set Approach and Timbral Transformation

One notable characteristic of the tape part's timbre is that, through various transformations, the recorded cello sounds, particularly those written for the cello part, are transformed into something more percussive than a cello. Many of these sounds resemble taiko drums, a percussion instrument used in Noh and other musical genres. Interestingly, the score features two notes, a major seventh interval between the lowest C and B, played pizzicato. However, a closer analysis of the actual sound reveals that the pitches written in the score are occasionally altered.

At the beginning of the Part 1, the cello pizzicato notes, altered to sound percussive, differ from the notated [C-B]. Instead, the rhythm begins with a high note close to [F]. At the end of the fourth measure, a low note close to [C] is added, followed by an even higher [B]. The pitch set is close to [C-F-B] from bottom to top. In terms of pitch, this is a perfect fourth plus an augmented fourth, the same as the latter of the two sets of three notes presented at the beginning of Schoenberg's "Piano Piece, Op. 11-1." The introduction of this pitch-class set at the beginning subtly establishes the harmony that shapes the piece's atmosphere.

Then, a flute resonates like a dragon flute, producing the pitch-class set [E-F#-C]. At the end of this section, in m10, the final three notes of the descending, fine quintuplet phrase continue with the pitch class set [E#-C-B], which matches the pitch of the three faint percussive notes at the beginning of the cello pizzicato.

While it may be questionable why electroacoustic sounds should be able to be produced precisely, yet they are not pursued as such, Toyama, educated at the École Normale de Musique and the Paris Conservatoire, should have exceptional solfège ability and would not have missed the subtle inconsistency. The subtle shifts and fluctuations in sound could be said to constitute the sonic sensation of gagaku, which is not based on fixed sounds.

6. Fusion of Traditional Japanese Music and Contemporary Western Music

As the album's title suggests, Toyama's creative intent was to incorporate and fuse traditional Japanese music with the idiom of contemporary Western music. In fact, both of the album's electroacoustic pieces use classical Japanese literature as narration text. The commentary for "Aoi No Ue," released the same year as "Waka," includes the following statement:

My intention is to create a new kind of musical drama using elements from traditional Japanese music such as "Gagaku," "Noh music," or Buddhist chanting.⁴

In other words, it's clear that she draws musical elements from traditional Japanese music, such as gagaku, noh, and chanting. However, Toyama possessed an extraordinary talent for Western music, having studied piano, a quintessential Western instrument, from a young age and traveling to Paris at 17 to study. Normally, once one's ear is trained in 12-tone equal temperament, it becomes extremely difficult to accurately appreciate music played in subtle pitch fluctuations, such as in gagaku and Noh. However, it should be remembered that Toyama was already 45 years old and a mid-career composer when she composed "Waka" and "Aoi No Ue." Given her birth year of 1913, she likely had more exposure to traditional music than musicians of today. Born into a wealthy family, Toyama likely attended concerts of these arts as part of her daily life, and she likely had opportunities to actually learn traditional instruments. While studying Western music on the piano, she likely also retained a foundation in traditional instruments, and these two cultures merged quite naturally, mediated by Toyama's intellect and sensibility.

7. Tone and Acoustic Techniques

The 12th bar of Waka-Part 1 features a sound similar to that of the gagaku sho. The sho is a free-reed wind instrument, and the only instrument in the gagaku ensemble capable of playing long chords. It consists of 17 bamboo tubes. Air is blown through the mouthpiece into the bellows, vibrating 15 reeds that actually produce the sound. Holes at the bottom of the tubes are covered with fingers to select notes and create chords. This process resembles additive synthesis. If we consider the production environment in 1958, without the RCA Mark II, sounds would likely have been created using a combination of several oscillators. The resulting sounds were then layered by dubbing onto tape to create the sound of a chord. Composers of that time learned the cut-and-splicing technique and electroacoustic music creation in an analog studio, where it took hours to create even a single short sound. Toyama must have also had the knowledge and skills to complete this work within less than a year of the CPEMC's official founding in 1958.

8. Waka as a Love Story

What perspective was taken in selecting the waka poems used in this work? They were chosen from the Hyakunin Isshu, a collection of 100 poems by 100 poets. The Hyakunin Isshu, strictly speaking, is a collection of 100 poems by 100 poets. The collection compiled mainly during the Kamakura period is famous, but there are many different collections from different eras, from those compiled by imperial decree to those compiled by private individuals. In this study, in parallel with the musical analysis, I also looked into the content of the waka poems. Surprisingly, the poems chosen were written by authors from different eras and by different people, but when lined up, something like a love story emerges.

⁴ Liner notes: TOYAMA, Michiko. "Waka and Other Compositions: Contemporary Music of Japan. Based on Traditional Japanese Themes and Poetry Composed by Michiko Toyama". Washington DC, Smithsonian Folkways Recordings (FW8881), 2007.

Waka-Part 1: Literal English translation based on modern Japanese interpretation

This evening, the faint sound of the wind rustling through the small grove of bamboo in my garden.

A mist hangs over the spring fields, and my heart sinks into sadness. A nightingale sings in this twilight.

The rumor has already spread that I am in love. I had only just begun to harbor these feelings secretly, without anyone knowing.

I tried to keep it hidden in my heart, but it seems to have shown on my face and in my expression. My love has become so obvious that people are asking me, "Are you perhaps thinking about someone you're in love with?"

Like the white clouds flowing over the lush green mountains, please don't let anyone notice by smiling openly and revealing your feelings.

Waka-Part 2: Literal English translation based on modern Japanese interpretation

I will not comb my disheveled morning hair with a comb. It has been touched by the hand of my beloved, the hand that served as my pillow.

You, with whom I spent the entire night and exchanged vows. After you left the next morning, I received a parting poem from you that said, "I will love you forever and always," but how true are those words? After we parted, I cannot fathom your heart, and like my disheveled black hair, my heart is in turmoil, filled with worry and anxiety.

Finally, the dawn peeks through the gaps in the shutters. How heartless it is, like the night!

Like the salt being burned at the time of the evening calm at Matsuho Bay, my body is burning with longing for the one who will not come to me.

We finally met again after so long, but you hastily left in the short time it took for me to even realize it was you. Just like the midnight moon that quickly hides behind the clouds.

It's not a love that will easily disappear, like the river mist that always lingers in the eddies of the Asuka River.

A storm blows through the garden, tempting and scattering the cherry blossoms. What falls like snow is not the flowers. It is my aging body.

Overall, the story can be further interpreted as follows:

Feeling the gentle sound of the wind at dusk and seeing the spring haze, the lady's heart sinks into sadness. Rumors have spread about their secret love, and she worries if her feelings have shown on her face. But as if to shake it off, she lives positively, with her love clearly defined. Even the morning after they are united, she struggles with the realities of a woman's heart, unable to understand their partner's feelings. After many troubled nights, as dawn finally arrives, she cries out, "It's as cruel as the night!" She yearns for someone who never comes, and yearns for the loneliness of finally meeting him, only to be suddenly gone, but she says that this love will not fade away as easily as the mist on a river. Finally, as she contemplates the cherry blossoms blown away by the storm, she concludes with a sense of resignation, saying, "It's not the flowers that fall like snow. It's my own body, growing old."

Viewed in this way, we see the image of a woman yearning for her beloved, yet resigned to her own aging and enduring it. Perhaps Toyama randomly selected 12 waka poems from the hundreds written by ancient intellectuals to weave a love story, then superimposed her own circumstances and feelings onto them.

The poem, whose authorship is unknown, begins with the lines, "After many turbulent nights (longing to see you but unable to), when dawn finally arrives, I cry out, 'It is as cruel as the night!'" It then concludes, "It is not flowers that fall like snow. It is my aging body," in a state of resignation. Perhaps it is a woman approaching the latter half of her life who has fallen in love. A love that will never come to fruition. And, "This love will not disappear as easily as river mist." If this were Toyama's own story, it would be deeply painful and sad.

In 1960, Toyama recorded a self-penned album, a culmination of her entire musical career, and returned to Japan for good. After returning to Japan, she did not return to Osaka College of Music, but instead studied acoustics at the Department of Electronic Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Kyoto University, and the University of Tokyo. Because she focused on acoustics research rather than composition, no musical works have been publicly released since then. Even the instrumental pieces included in the record have not been published yet.

Why did she disappear from the world of composition? The reality is that, due to gender and political considerations, Toyama's future as a composer may have been closed off. After composing "Waka" and "Aoi No Ue" at the CPEMC, Toyama hoped to remain in New York and continue creating music, but her application for a Rockefeller Foundation grant was rejected. Furthermore, she continued to be ignored by those associated with the CPEMC. In 1960, with the cooperation of the Japan Society, she recorded an album for Smithsonian Folkways Records, but she was unable to return to the United States and had to remain in Japan.

"Yamato No Koe," which won an ISCM award in 1937, was not performed in Japan until 1993, a whopping 56 years later. Toyama's desired live-electronic version of "Waka" with a narrator on stage has yet to be premiered.

9. Conclusion

As the female composer Michiko Toyama gained attention, many contemporary Japanese composers were surprised to learn that in 1937, Toyama's earliest piece brought her a prize at the ISCM-WMD. Furthermore, thanks to "Waka," it became clear that she was the first Japanese female composer, and possibly the first Asian female composer, to compose electroacoustic music. Incidentally, Toshiro Mayuzumi, who studied at the Paris Conservatoire immediately after graduating from Tokyo University of the Arts, composed Japan's first musique concrète work, "X, Y, Z," in Tokyo in 1952 after returning to Japan. However, as mentioned above, Toyama's work was conceived and composed as something closer to a live-electronic piece. Considering its time, it was an extremely forward-thinking and visionary endeavor. One cannot help but wonder whether, because it was so forward-thinking, the very existence and significance of this work have been lost to history and political pressure.

As mentioned before, it is actually extremely difficult to meaningfully and beautifully combine Western music, which is fundamentally based on 12-tone equal temperament, with traditional Japanese music, which includes instruments like the shinobue, rich in subtle microtones and

even deliberately engineered to not produce octaves. This is because, after studying Western music for a long time, one first perfects the ability to grasp sounds in 12-tone equal temperament through solfège. In a sense, the interval quantized to 12-tone equal temperament makes it extremely difficult to perceive subtle pitch fluctuations as beautiful or charming. This has been pointed out by many subsequent Japanese composers who base their compositions on Western musical idioms.

So how can these two be integrated? In Toyama's case, her approach to electroacoustic music as a mature composer trained in traditional Western compositional techniques may have been beneficial given her limited time. However, one of the best solutions would be to actively incorporate musical elements outside of traditional harmonic methods, such as rich microtonal gestures and organic rhythms, rather than being limited to harmony based on fixed pitches and triads. It has become clear that many such attempts are evident in Toyama's tape music parts.

It is impressive to learn that Toyama, born over 100 years ago from today, pursued her own path in life, from pianist to composer to researcher, without being bound by Japanese society's outdated conventions regarding women. After studying in Paris twice during an era before airplanes, she arrived in New York two years before the founding of the CPEMC and began her research into the creation of electroacoustic music as a visiting composer at Columbia University. Tracing Toyama's unique life and revisiting "Waka" through the sheet music and recordings is truly meaningful, as all the seemingly separate puzzle pieces come together to form a single work of art.

Toyama was already 45 when she created "Waka" at the CPEMC, and through the waka poems in this work, she seems to have reached a state of mind reminiscent of life's transience. Reading the 12 poems together conveys the heart-wrenching feeling of putting into words the real feelings of a woman who has passed the halfway point in her life. Inferring from the carefully arranged poems in this work, one cannot help but suspect that Toyama must have experienced an enormous drama in her heart as she journeyed from Osaka to Paris to New York.

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